

MODULAR DECK SYSTEM FOR RORO VESSELS – RAMSSES H2020 R&D PROJECT

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Abstract

This paper will give an overview of the demonstration case Modular Deck System for RoRo Vessels developed within RAMSSES (Realisation and Demonstration of Advanced Material Solutions for Sustainable and Efficient Ships) EU funded project under HORIZON 2020. The research and development is addressed to the construction of internal strength decks on RoRo vessels introducing FRP (Fibre reinforced plastic) pultruded profiles and FRP sandwich technology. Reducing the weight of decks results in many benefits regarding general ship design due to large number of decks. Improved flexibility in the ship design, where weight could be traded for ship size, scantlings, cargo capacity, speed, installed power and weight, integration of structures and outfitting. Optimising the deck structure design using innovative materials and geometry results in more efficient production as well. With respect to ship operational aspects such as Fuel oil consumption and CO₂ emission reduction due to ship lightweight reduction leads to increased propulsion efficiency. The overall objective at RAMSSES is to develop optimised structure of RO-RO/Car-carrier using RAMSSES defined deck modules with respect to production optimisation as main objective followed by weight reduction, joint development, Fuel oil consumption and CO₂ emission reduction.

Key words: RAMSSES; RoRo vessel; pultruded profiles; lightweight; production optimisation

Sažetak

Članak daje pregled demonstracijskog slučaja modularnog sustava paluba RoRo brodova koji se razvija u sklopu projekta RAMSSES (Realisation and Demonstration of Advanced Material Solutions for Sustainable and Efficient Ships) koji je financiran sredstvima EU unutar HORIZON 2020. Istraživanje i razvoj unutar ove radne cjeline odnose se na konstrukciju unutarnjih paluba RoRo brodova. Smanjenje težina paluba stvara mnoge prednosti na opće karakteristike broda s obzirom da ti tipovi brodova imaju značajan broj paluba. Neke od prednosti su fleksibilnost prilikom osnivanja broda gdje se smanjenjem težine mogu povećati same dimenzije, korisna nosivost, brzina, ili smanjiti potrebna porivna snaga te bolja integracija strukture i opreme. Optimiziranjem strukture palube primjenom inovativnih materijala i geometrije rezultira i efikasnijom proizvodnjom. Ako se promatra brod u službi, smanjenje potrošnje goriva i smanjenje CO₂ zbog smanjene težine broda, dovodi do povećanja propulzijske efikasnosti. Sveobuhvatni cilj unutar RAMSSES-a je razviti optimiziranu strukturu RO-RO broda odnosno broda za prijevoz automobila primjenom RAMSSES palubnih modula kroz optimizaciju proizvodnje kao primarni cilj, uz dodatne ciljeve smanjenja težina, zajedničkog razvoja te smanjenja potrošnje goriva i ispuštanja CO₂.

Ključne riječi: RAMSSES; RoRo brod; pultrudirani profili; smanjenje težine; proizvodnje optimizacija

1 Introduction

Imperative on efficient transportation drives the development of new lightweight structural solutions with the goal of energy consumption and greenhouse gasses emissions reduction. This paper will give an overview of the Work package 14's Modular Deck System for RoRo Vessels, which is one of thirteen demonstration cases developed within the R&D project RAMSSES (Realisation and Demonstration of Advanced Material Solutions for Sustainable and Efficient Ships), funded by the European Union's HORIZON 2020 framework programme under grant agreement No 723246.

The research and development presented is addressed to the construction of internal strength decks on RoRo vessels introducing FRP (Fiber reinforced plastic) pultruded profiles and FRP sandwich technology. The development started back in the 2006. during the R&D project Delight Transport, funded by the European Union's FP6 framework programme, where a design of a composite car deck has been developed, using sandwich technology. Five years after the project end, the benefits of the solution have been recognized by a shipowner, which results with a successful implementation on the Car carrier m/v SIEM CICERO for the construction of three fixed car decks, built and delivered at Uljanik Shipyard in the 2017. The inovative design from CICERO has been used as a starting point for the further development in RAMSSES project,. The project started in 2017. and will be finished in 2021.

1.1 Problem definition

RoRo vessels have numerous internal strength decks. Clearances between decks are fixed and defined by cargo requirements (height of cars, trucks). Reducing the weight of decks results in many benefits regarding general ship design due to large number of decks (lower ship height, lower vertical centre of gravity (VCG), lower equipment number etc.). Improved flexibility in the ship design, where weight could be traded for ship size, scantlings, cargo capacity, speed, installed power and weight, integration of structures and outfitting. Optimising the deck structure design using innovative materials and geometry results in more efficient production as well (shorter lead times, improved reliability, and quality)

1.2 Technical approach

With respect to ship operational aspects such as fuel oil consumption and CO2 emission reduction ship lightweight reduction leads to increased propulsion efficiency. In addition, depending on the design requirements, main engine installed power can be reduced for the same cargo intake or cargo intake can be increased. Reduced ship weight in the ship upper zone leads to better stability performance and less ballast required to fulfil stability requirements, where the total cargo in take can be additionally increased.

The first step to the full application of RAMSSES modules was to implement the hybrid transport structure approach with steel and GRP profiles application in the design and production of deck structures. The overall objective was to develop optimised structure of a Vehicle carrier using RAMSSES defined deck modules with respect to production optimisation as main objective followed by weight reduction, joint development, fuel oil consumption and CO2 emission reduction.

The innovative design was evaluated with respect to the conventional steel design as well as to the alternative design using GRP sandwich panels already implemented at Uljanik newbuilding No 513 (m/v SIEM CICERO, delivered June 2017), Figure 1., which was used as base design for the developments at RAMSSES.

Figure 1 *Uljanik newbuilding No 513 (m/v SIEM CICERO, delivered June 2017).*

1.3 Results and achievements

In the novel RAMSSES design fixed car decks on a Car Carrier were designed by implementing composite modules using FRP pultruded profiles technology. Uljanik newbuilding No 513 (Car Carrier m/v SIEM Cicero) was chosen as base design, where innovative deck structure design, including composite sandwich panels is implemented at Decks 10, 11 and 12.

Full application of RAMSSES modules started with the implementation of the new developed module using pultruded profile technology by replacing the composite sandwich panel on a base design. In addition, alternative deck structure designs were recognised for further development at RAMSSES.

The first step was to define the data needed for the design such as deck structure arrangement, boundary condition, loading and design criteria.

Followed by the design alternatives assessment in the detail design stage, RAMSSES deck was further developed.

With respect to the production and assembly process, assessment on the integration of the RAMSSES design alternative into shipyard process was performed considering several scenarios. Further adjustments will be done according to the data collected from the full scale demonstrator production process.

New developed designs were evaluated with respect to the conventional steel design as well as to the composite design implemented on Uljanik newbuilding No 513 (base design).

Finally, the novel structural design will be further evaluated through laboratory tests (mechanical tests, full-scale and small-scale fire tests) as well as tests on the full-scale demonstrator.

At this stage of the project the production of the small scale and full-scale specimens is ongoing. Preparations for the full-scale demonstrator were performed and the production started.

2 Requirements and case definition

2.1 Case definition

The purpose of this application case is to reduce the production cost and lead time as well as to decrease the weight of the three upper decks (decks 10, 11 and 12) in a Car carrier; see Figure 2. This way both the structural weight of the ship and the vertical centre of gravity will be also lowered. Clearances between decks are fixed and defined by cargo requirements (height of cars, trucks). Reducing height and weight of deck structures is a very demanding task but it can result in many benefits regarding general ship design due to large number of decks (lower ship height, lower VCG, lower equipment number etc.).

Figure 2 *Uljanik newbuilding No 513 – composite decks 10,11 and 12*

In a conventional steel design a cargo deck is designed with steel deck plating stiffened by transversal web frames and longitudinal stiffeners. In the Innovative deck structure design at Uljanik newbuilding No 513 (base design), composite structure is implemented at Decks 10, 11 and 12. The structure arrangement consists of steel supporting grillage and composite sandwich panels (GRP, with PVC core, vacuum infused), Figure 3, Figure 4. Composite panel connection to supporting structure is designed as flexible with bolts. Same deck design will be base design for further development at RAMSSES.

Figure 3 *Composite sandwich panel*

Figure 4 *Uljanik newbuilding No 513 – decks 10,11 and 12 view*

2.1.1 Technical approach

The way to the full application of RAMSSES modules was to implement the new developed module using pultruded profile technology analysing different design alternatives, which can be defined as follows:

1. Composite module designed to replace the composite sandwich panel according the base design (small composite module)
2. Composite module designed to replace the composite sandwich panel and part of steel supporting structure according to the base design (large composite module)

The first step was to develop a composite module using pultruded profile technology by replacing the composite panel in the base design (Design alternative 1). In parallel to the First design alternative possibilities for further design development was investigated. Such as possibility to use FRP pultruded profiles for part of supporting structure, made of steel on base design, combination of different designs such as steel, composite sandwich panels and extruded profiles as well (Design alternative 2). Hypothetic design solutions investigated are illustrated on Figure 5 to Figure 8.

Figure 5 Design alternative 1 – composite module hypothetical design solution –cross section)

Figure 6 Design alternative 1 – steel structure arrangement – Deck top view

On the contrary if the catalysis is too slow, the material will be released from the die yet gelled and the tensile force to which it will be subjected will cause the deformation of the profile.

The mechanical properties of the profiles depend on the quantity and type of raw materials (resins and fibers) that are used.

Many resin types may be used in pultrusion: both thermosetting (polyester, epoxy, acrylic, vinylester, etc.), thermoplastic (PVC, polyurethane, polyethylene, etc.) and various type of reinforced fibers.

FRP profiles made with the pultrusion process have excellent mechanical properties (such as tensile strength) in the direction of the fibers, unlike the mechanical properties in the transverse direction that are low. To increase the mechanical properties in the transverse direction is possible to add reinforcing mats (with fibers arranged in two or more preferential directions) in the composite mixture.

Extruded profiles and production facilities are illustrated on Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 9 *Extruded profiles production facilities*

Figure 10 *Extruded profiles - examples*

2.1.3 FRP Profiles Properties

Profiles can be realized in various sections, shapes and colors, with constant cross-section along the length.

Use of FRP pultruded profiles can bring the following benefits: reduced weight, low assembly and transportation costs, reduced maintenance cost as maintenance is not required,

significant corrosion and chemical resistance, electric and thermal insulation, insonorization, operational range (temperatures from -40°C to $+120^{\circ}\text{C}$), high mechanical resistance, acoustic insulation, electromagnetic transparency, durability.

Raw materials used in pultrusion process can be categorized as follows:

1. Thermosetting Resins: Polyester, Vinylester, Epoxy. Acrylic
2. Reinforcements
 - a. Layout: Rovings, Mats, Reinforcing Mats, Wovens
 - b. Type: Glass, Carbon, Aramidic, Polyester, Natural
3. Fillers: Calcium carbonate, Quartz, Kaolin
4. Catalysts and additive

2.2 Requirements

2.2.1 Geometry requirements

The composite module is to be designed to cover the opening formed by a load carrying steel grillage structure to form a deck surface. Composite modules are to be the same for all considered decks.

Geometry of the steel supporting structure will be defined according to the design alternative.

Supporting structure constraints are:

- Length between deck transverses, $LT = 13600\text{ mm}$,
- Breadth between deck longitudinal girders is not a constraint, at base design $BL = 1750\text{ mm}$,
- Height, including structure height, building tolerance and static deflection (cargo load only, without own weight and without dynamic acceleration), $H = 330\text{ mm}$
- Transverse girder flange breadth BFT, is not a constraint, at base design $BFT = 350\text{ mm}$
- Longitudinal girder flange breadth BFT, is not a constraint, at base design $BFL = 180\text{ mm}$

Opening in steel grillage dimensions to be covered with composite module:

- Length between deck transverses flange, $LC = LT - BFT$
- Breadth between deck longitudinal girder flange, $BC = BL - BFL$
- Radius at opening corners, to be defined

Composite module constraints between girders are:

- Height above deck plating line to be max. 5 mm

FRP profiles geometry constraints with respect to production:

- Height $> 0.5\text{ m}$
- Breadth $> 1.2\text{ m}$

Cargo lashing opening arrangement:

- transversal distance between openings: 600 - 900 mm

- longitudinal distance between openings: 600 -700 mm

2.2.2 Boundary Conditions

Boundary conditions are to be investigated as they have influence on the connection detail design with respect to FRP structure arrangement.

Boundary is considered as simply supported on the base design, due to the realistic nature of the interaction between sandwich panel and supporting grillage.

2.2.3 Loading

The cargo loading is defined and shown on Figure 11.

NAME	LOAD AT	AXLE LOAD (t)	TYRE PRINT (mm)	HOMOGENOUS LOADING (t/m ²)	DECK NO
PRIVATE CAR	SEA	<p>L=4.8 m B=1.9 m</p>	0.20	1 3 5 10 11 12 13	

Figure 11 Load cases – vehicle parking position

With respect to the connection of the composite module to supporting structure, load case found to be critical is when four lashing forces acting on composite module not loaded with cargo in ship transverse direction.

2.3 Technical challenges

Main technical challenge foreseen is a design of a robust composite module that will allow standard shipbuilding tolerances at the steel part of the structure combined with an improved composite/steel arrangement, compared to the base design) with respect to:

- production (less complex steel structure arrangement, building blocks, etc)
- assembly (transport, joints)
- cargo operation (flush deck, lashing)
- cost (decreased production cost)

3 Product design

3.1 Concept design

Concept design is defined as the phase in structural design when geometry and topology are open to modification and structural variants are analyzed in accordance with the needs of the head designer. Benefits of optimization procedure in this phase are the biggest. For the concept designs, steel and composite part have been optimized with respect to weight, arrangement, connection and fire safety.

The first step was to develop the deck profile using pultruded profile technology, which is similar for all design alternatives considered at RAMSSES. In parallel to deck profile,

possibilities for further design development have been investigated, such as possibility to use FRP pultruded profiles for part of supporting structure, made of steel on base design.

Starting from the two design alternatives, five concept designs were developed and analyzed:

- 2 FRP profile types, FRP deck profile and FRP boundary, small composite module
- 1A 1 FRP profile type, small composite module
- 3 FRP profile types, FRP deck and FRP supporting profile, medium composite module
- 2A 3 FRP profile types, FRP deck and FRP supporting profile, large composite module
- 1 FRP profile type, FRP deck profile, large composite module (combination of 1 and 2)

For each design concept both steel and composite structure arrangement were defined where deck arrangement consists of the composite module supported by the steel grillage. Steel grillage is supported by two rows of pillars. Steel grillage and composite module arrangement have been varied resulting in five concept designs, illustrated on Figure 12.

Figure 12 Concept designs developed at RAMSSES

3.1.1 Steel structure

For the design concepts, deck structure arrangement optimization has been performed with respect to weight, outfitting, production technology and cost.

Structure scantlings have been checked according to BV Rules and Regulations.

Arrangement of the steel beams has been varied in order to evaluate different sizes of the composite module. Main constraints were the pillar arrangement, ship side structure, outfitting (arrangement of the CO₂ fire distinguishing system, two lines in longitudinal direction) and maximum allowable deflection of the structure.

3D beam structural analysis has been performed for the steel structure scantlings determination, for concept designs with medium and large module (2, 2A, 3), using DNV software NAUTICUS 3D Beam. For the concept designs with small module, structure scantlings from base design have been considered.

3.1.2 Composite structure

Depending on the design concept, different profile types and geometry for each type were considered. Composite profile types can be divided as follows:

Deck profile – forming composite module surface

Supporting profile – used as support of the deck profile and for connection to the steel structure

3.1.3 Design concept assessment

Selection of most promising concept designs for further development have been performed according to preliminary weight estimation, preliminary production cost analysis and production process criteria.

Summary of the assessment can be found below:

- 1
 - weight reduction of 8 % compared to the conventional steel deck
 - Increased weight for 17 % compared to the base design
 - Reduced deck production cost for 15 %
 - Simple transport and assembly of composite module on board
- 1A
 - No weight reduction compared to the conventional steel deck
 - Increased weight for 25 % compared to the base design
 - No production cost savings compared to the base design
 - Simple transport and assembly of composite module on board
- 2
 - weight reduction of 10 % compared to the conventional steel deck
 - increased weight for 15 % compared to base design
 - Reduced deck production cost for 18 % compared to the base design
 - Flexibility in the lashing holes arrangement
 - Special attention to be paid on the transport and assembly of composite module on board
- 2A
 - Too big deflections of FRP supporting girders i.e. design of FRP supporting girders is not applicable
- 3
 - weight reduction of 10 % compared to the conventional steel deck

- o increased weight for 15 % compared to base design with GRP sandwich modules
- o Reduced deck production cost for 20 % compared to the base design
- o Flexibility in the lashing holes arrangement
- o Special attention to be paid on the transport and assembly of composite module on board
- o Special attention to be paid on the interaction of the FRP module and steel supporting structure

Concept design 3 has been chosen for the detail design stage and further development. Main arguments that outweighed to concept design 3 are:

- size of the composite module – large composite module, bigger challenge at RAMSSES
- promising weight and production cost assessment results,
- number of different pultruded profiles used

Starting from the two design alternatives defined in the early project stage, five concept designs have been developed and analyzed where one has been selected for further development in the detail design stage: Concept design 3.

3.2 *Detail design*

Following concept design assessment results in the detail design stage RAMSSES deck has been further developed. Starting from the Concept design 3 deck arrangement (geometry and topology) the optimisation has been concentrated on refined structure scantlings optimisation for both steel and composite module, definition of specific details with respect to outfitting (connection details, lashing) and fire safety, following the RAMSSES objectives.

Deck arrangement consists of the composite module supported by the steel grillage system and fixed part of steel arranged on the side shell and in the central part of the deck in way of the pillars (executed as a large box girder)). Composite module supporting steel grillage system consists of longitudinal girders (composite module supports) supported by transverse girders. Transverse girders are supported by the fixed part of the deck on the side and box girder in way of the pillars. In order to obtain a flat deck i.e. composite module and steel plating upper surfaces on the same level, the steel grillage supporting system is arranged in two heights. As composite module supports, longitudinal steel girders are lower in height where bottom edge is in line with the transverse steel girders and central box girders. At the central box girders and fixed deck at side shell, a flat bar is arranged to support the composite module. Bolt or riveted connection system of the Composite module to longitudinal supports is foreseen. Deck arrangement is illustrated on Figure 13 and Figure 14.

Figure 13 RAMSSES deck arrangement

Figure 14 RAMSSES deck arrangement – cross sections

The first step was to finalise the composite deck profile design. Further, possible design improvements on the steel grillage supporting system have been investigated. Starting from the deck arrangement described above a second design alternative has been developed and analysed, where the main objective was to improve the design in way of production and connection between steel and composite module. Hence, steel grillage system where the height of the transverse girder reduced to be aligned with the longitudinal girders is developed. For both grillage arrangements, composite module and connection system is the same.

3.2.1 Steel structure arrangement and calculation

Deck structure arrangement optimization has been performed with respect to weight, outfitting, production technology and cost. Structure scantlings have been checked according to BV Rules and Regulations.

Arrangement of the steel beams from the concept design 3 has been further optimized, varying girder geometry (width, thickness, height, profile type: box, T). From the optimization results, two arrangements are selected for further assessment and final selection which can be presented as follows:

1. Grillage system in two levels, Figure 14
2. Grillage system in one level, Figure 15

Figure 15 RAMSSES deck arrangement – grillage system alternative 2 - cross sections

3D beam structural analysis has been performed for the steel structure scantlings determination, using DNV software NAUTICUS 3D Beam. Grillage model is illustrated on Figure 16. Finally, Grillage system in two levels was selected for further developments. FEA will be performed to further optimize the structure.

Figure 16 3D beam – deck steel grillage model

3.2.2 Composite module optimisation

The driver of the optimisation was based on the requirements to reduce the deformability of the FRP structure from one side and to extend the use of FRP as much as possible in order to reduce the overall weight. For solving this issue, it was decided to adopt a hybrid structure deck with steel beams supporting higher continuous FRP profiles (Concept design 3).

Deck profile geometry definition is led by production process technology restrictions and lashing opening arrangement requirements. The profile section is arranged in order to assure both the torsional stiffness of the deck and lashing opening outfitting, where the geometry had to be arranged for the lashing hole outfitting (steel protection) and cargo lashing equipment (hook) that require a thin surface. The contact area to be glued is articulated with a shear key shape in order to increase the connection between the profiles. Deck profile and Composite module geometry and arrangement are illustrated on and Figure 17 and Figure 18
Composite module arrangement

Calculation input data have been considered. Finite element analysis has been performed. The tool used to evaluate the FRP deck panel was SAP2000. Structure is discretized with combination of solid (frame) and shell elements. Deck profile is modelled with shell elements and deck profile supporting structure is modelled with solid (frame) elements. Calculation

model is shown on Figure 19, where yellow represents the deck profile and blue represents the steel girders, deck module supporting structure. Typical load schemes are shown on Figure 20.

Figure 17 *Pultruded profile geometry*

Figure 18 *Composite module arrangement*

Figure 19 *FEA - Deck profile calculation model*

Figure 20 FEA - Load Scheme

Calculation results showed that the stress and deflection values are within the required limits. Calculation results are illustrated on Figure 21 and Figure 22.

Figure 21 FEA –stresses result overview: Load case1 (left), Load case 2 (Centre), Load case3 (Right)

Figure 22 FEA –deflection result overview: Load case1 (left), Load case 2 (Centre), Load case3 (Right)

3.2.3 Connections

In the detail design stage connections were developed and optimized. Final connection solution between structural members was selected, which can be divided as follows:

Steel to steel

Standard shipbuilding welded connection.

Composite to composite

FRP pultruded profiles are bonded to each other in order to form a composite module to be assembled on the steel supporting structure. The connection area geometry of the profiles is additionally designed to improve the connection.

Composite to steel

Composite module riveted connection has been selected for further development. The connections are designed to withstand the design forces; deck load, local cargo lashing and global forces (deflections).

With respect to the connection of the composite module to supporting structure, load case found to be critical is when four lashing forces acting on composite module not loaded with cargo in ship transverse direction.

For the connection equipment, the expansion bolt (HOLLO BOLT) has been selected as final solution.

a) Hexagonal

a) Hexagonal		Clamping Thickness W mm	Outer Ply min t mm	Sleeve		Collar			Tightening Torque Nm	Safe Working Loads (5:1 Factor of Safety)	
Product Code	Bolt Length B mm			Length L mm	Outer \varnothing S mm	Height H mm	\varnothing D mm	A/F mm		Tensile kN	Single Shear kN
HB08-1	M8 x 50	3 - 22	-	30	13.75	5	22	19	23	4.0	5.0
HB08-2	M8 x 70	22 - 41	-	49	13.75	5	22	19	23	4.0	5.0

Figure 23 Selected HOLLO BOLT

3.2.4 Fire safety assessment

According to the requirements and experience from fire safety assessment conducted at the base design, RAMSSES deck arrangement has been preliminary evaluated. Main objective in order to improve fire safety properties is to execute the deck as much as possible gas tight. Critical points are openings in deck at cargo lashing equipment and at composite module boundaries.

To reduce the openings, different solutions are available either structural or outfitting. Final decision will be taken according to the fire tests results, where two different full scale specimens will be tested.

3.2.5 Weight calculation

After the structural calculation and optimization were performed, the weight calculation was done where the RAMSSES design was compared versus the conventional steel design and base design. Deck area considered in the calculation represents the part of the novel deck design including the composite modules and steel supporting structure i.e. modified structure arrangement compared to the conventional design. Selected deck areas are illustrated on 24, 25 and 26. Total deck weight summary is shown in Table 1.

Figure 24 *Conventional steel deck*

Figure 25 *Base design-composite GRP sandwich panels and steel*

Figure 26 *Ramsses design - composite FRP pultruded profiles and steel*

Table 1 Weight calculation summary

	Conventional design - steel	Base design - Sandwich panels	RAMSSES design - pultruded FRP profiles
SPECIFIC WEIGHT			
Steel weight, kg/m ²	80.3	48.01	50.43
Composite weight, kg/m ²	0	13.07	18.59
Total weight, kg/m ²	80.3	61.08	69.02
Total area (3 decks)	13290	13290	13290
TOTAL WEIGHT			
composite weight	0	174	247
steel weight, tonnes	1067	638	670
weight, tones	1067	812	917
RELATIVE DIFFERENCE			
composite weight	/	0%	42%
steel weight	67%	0%	5%
total weight	31%	0%	13%
RELATIVE DIFFERENCE			
composite weight/total	0%	16%	23%
steel weight	0%	-40%	-37%
total weight	0%	-24%	-14%

4 Process engineering

This chapter will summarize the possible production and assembly process for the design alternative of GFRP composite panels which study is ongoing at the time of writing this article.

For the production process of pultrusion profile, two business models are analyzed where there are possibilities to produce the pultrusion panel in the shipyard or in a specialized factory out of the shipyard. According to the business models it has been determined what is the best approach to produce the pultrusion profile in term of time and cost from production and transportation point of view.

For the assembly process in the shipyard, the analysis on the lead time, resources, and the constraints in shipyards to enable the integration of design alternative panels into current assembly process has been performed, by using the Simulation Toolkit Shipbuilding (STS) of the Siemens simulation software Plant Simulation.

The hole process is applied on the different areas of the shipyard. In the STS the transportation by crane, forklift and carrier is also included in the simulation, so the time and therefore the lead costs of the drivers have been included in the resources of all personal statistics. As there are already methods for joining blocks or sections it is very suitable using this tool for the installation of the panels to the blocks as well as for the bonding process.

During the preparation of the simulation, total five scenarios were considered with respect to the composite module preassembly and assembly location. The scenarios have been reduced to two, as the installation after ship launching is restricted to the panel size. The first

scenario is considering joining of all panels in the workshop and install them all in the slipway. The second scenario is analyzing the process to install the panels in the pre-block assembly. As there are restrictions of the hot work, this is not applicable for all the panels to some needs also be installed afterwards. It is examined that the second scenario will take more time but also avoiding the bottleneck in the slipway.

The complete process of assembly scenario 1 and 2 can be seen in Figure 27 *Pultrusion panel assembly process for scenario 1, and 2*

Figure 27 *Pultrusion panel assembly process for scenario 1, and 2*

5 Demonstrator and Testing

The demonstrator was designed to represent the typical RAMSSES deck structure in full scale, as marked with red square on Figure 28.

Building and assembly process for the demonstrator will be equal to the process to be used in the shipyard, where feedback will be given to the production process assessment.

Figure 28 Typical deck layout

At the time of writing this article, the demonstrator production was ongoing. Steel component under construction is illustrated on Figure 29. Pultrusion facilities including the RAMSSES component forming dye and profile specimen are illustrated on Figure 30 and Figure 31.

Figure 29 Demonstrator – steel structure under construction

Figure 30 Pultrusion process – RAMSSES forming dye

Figure 31 RAMSSES FRP profile

Several test arrangements are planned and specified as follows:

- Bonding test
- Small scale fire tests
- Full scale fire tests
- Mechanical tests
- Tests on the demonstrator

Figure 32 *Test specimens*

6 Conclusion

In the novel RAMSSES design fixed car decks 10 to 12 on a Car Carrier were designed implementing composite modules using FRP pultruded profiles technology. Uljanik newbuilding No 513 (m/v SIEM Cicero) was used as base design. At the base design, innovative deck structure design, including composite sandwich panels has been implemented at Decks 10, 11 and 12.

The first step was to create the data needed to design the composite modules at decks 10-12. In addition, Deck structure arrangement, boundary condition, loading and design criteria were defined.

Full application of RAMSSES modules started with the implementation of the new developed module using pultruded profile technology where different design alternatives were investigated. Following the design alternatives assessment results in the detail design stage RAMSSES deck was further developed. Deck optimisation was concentrated on the composite module optimisation with respect to weight, outfitting (connection details, lashing) and fire safety, following the RAMSSES objectives. Steel structure was optimised with respect to the production process (arrangement) as main objective, resulting in two different designs. Further, with respect to fire safety, improvements on both steel and composite module were considered. Finally, the solutions were evaluated and final design selected where specific composite module details with respect to fire safety will be finally selected after the fire tests results. Weight calculation was performed, where the results are in line with the expected. In addition, Demonstrator was designed to represent the final RAMSSES deck design in full scale.

With respect to the production and assembly process, assessment on the integration of the RAMSSES design alternative into shipyard process was performed considering several scenarios.

New developed design was evaluated with respect to the conventional steel design as well as to the composite design implemented on Uljanik newbuilding No 513.

Finally, the novel structural design will be further evaluated through laboratory tests results (mechanical tests, fire tests), full scale tests on the demonstrator and lessons learned with respect to the full-scale demonstrator production process.

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